

Microbial study, molecular docking, Fukui functions and RDG analysis of 3, 4-chlorophenyl acetic acid

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Abstract

The structure and several spectroscopic features along with reactivity parameters of 4-chlorophenylacetic acid (CPA) have been studied using experimental techniques and tools derived from quantum chemical calculations. Structure optimization is followed by force field calculations based on density functional theory (DFT) at the B3LYP level of theory. Local reactivity descriptors such as Fukui functions and local softness's have also been calculated to find out the reactive sites within the molecule. Estimation of biological effects has been made on the basis of prediction of activity spectra for substances (PASS) prediction, docking results and the microbial study also reported. Weak interactions such as hydrogen bonding and Van der Waals interaction were analyzed via reduced density gradient (RDG) analysis in CPA.